

Graphs, Markov Chains, and Gene Networks

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1 Introduction

Graph theory (also called network analysis) is employed in many fields of applied mathematics: in statistics, graphs can be used to describe and analyze many properties of Markovian chains (1) and neural networks (2); in mechanics, they are employed to model kinematic chains (3), in biology the concept of protein-protein interaction finds an immediate translation into weighted graphs (4); in computer science, graph theory is among the theoretical bases of operations research (5). In this short document, I'll present some definitions and theorems and I introduce the basic functionality of `igraph`, an R package (6, 7). At the end of this document, I present an application of graph theory to the study of gene networks.

2 Undirected graphs

DEF. 1 (undirected graph). An undirected graph $\Gamma(V, E)$ is a finite set of vertices $V(\Gamma) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ and edges $E(\Gamma) = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\}$. Each edge is a connection between two nodes, therefore any edge of an undirected graph can be indicated by the unordered couple of nodes that are connected by it. The graph in Figure 1 has 5 vertices connected by 7 edges. Note that the connection of one vertex to itself is still an edge, and it goes under the name of *loop*. The loop, in our example, is the edge (v_4, v_4) . Note also that edge (v_i, v_j) is the same as edge (v_j, v_i) , since this is an undirected graph. Vertices can often be referred to as *nodes*. We'll use both terms, equivalently.

In R, this graph can be plotted with the following lines of code. You just need to specify the edges as a vector with $2|E|$ elements, where $|E|$ is the number of edges (the cardinality of the set of edges). The first two elements of the vector may be, in our case, 1 and 2, followed by 1 and 5, to account for the two edges connected to node v_1 ; and so forth.

```
# build the graph and plot it
edges<-c(1,2,1,5,2,3,3,5,4,5,4,3,4,4)
graph<-make_graph(edges=edges,directed=F)
plot(graph,vertex.size=20)
```

As this example suggests, once the names of the nodes are defined, an undirected graph is completely described by the vector of the edges.

DEF. 2 (adjacency matrix). An undirected graph with n vertices is completely described by a square matrix A of order n whose element a_{ij} assumes value 1 if the edge (v_i, v_j) is present, assumes value zero otherwise. The j -th diagonal element of A has value 1 if vertex j has a loop, zero otherwise. From the equivalence of edge (v_i, v_j) and edge (v_j, v_i) it follows that A is symmetric. Moreover, the sum of the elements of column i equals the number of edges connected to node i , and this sum is equal to the sum of the elements of row i . It is easy to recognize that the adjacency matrix of the graph in Figure 1 is the following one:

$$M_a = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

To plot the graph from the adjacency matrix in R, install and call package igraph. Then input the matrix and use it as in the following script:

Figure 1. Undirected graph, with 5 vertices, 7 edges, and one loop.

```
# adjacency matrix
aM<-matrix(0,nrow=5,ncol=5)
aM[1,]<-c(0,1,0,0,1)
aM[2,]<-c(1,0,1,0,0)
aM[3,]<-c(0,1,0,1,1)
aM[4,]<-c(0,0,1,1,1)
aM[5,]<-c(1,0,1,1,0)

graph<-graph_from_adjacency_matrix(aM,mode="undirected")
plot(graph,vertex.size=20)
```

DEF. 3 (incidence matrix). Another matrix representation of an undirected graph $\Gamma(V, E)$ is a matrix with a row for each edge and a column for each node, called incidence matrix. Element i, j of this

matrix is zero if edge e_i does not touch vertex v_j , it is 1 otherwise. Therefore, the incidence matrix of the graph in Figure 1 is

$$M_i = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Note that the row corresponding to a loop has only one element, while all the other rows have two elements. To my knowledge, it is not possible to directly input the incidence matrix in a function of package `igraph`. It is possible, though, to write a few lines of code that derive the adjacency matrix from the incidence one, and vice versa, as shown in the following two R functions.

```
# convert incidence matrix into adjacency matrix for undirected graphs
```

```
iM2aM<-function(iM) {
  V<-ncol(iM) # number of vertices
  aM<-matrix(0,nrow=V,ncol=V) # adjacency matrix
  for (e in 1:nrow(iM)) { # scan the edges
    temp<-which(iM[e,]!=0)
    if (length(temp)==2) {
      aM[temp[1],temp[2]]<-1
      aM[temp[2],temp[1]]<-1
    } else if (length(temp)==1) {
      aM[temp[1],temp[1]]<-1
    } else {
      stop("The incidence matrix is wrong!")
    }
  }
  return(aM)
}
```

```
# convert adjacency matrix into incidence matrix for undirected graphs
```

```
aM2iM<-function(aM) {
  V<-ncol(aM) # number of vertices
  E<-0
  for (i in 1:V) {
    for (j in i:V) {
      E<-E+aM[i,j] # number of edges
    }
  }
  iM<-matrix(0,nrow=E,ncol=V) # adjacency matrix
  k<-1
  for (i in 1:V) {
    for (j in i:V) {
      if (aM[i,j]==1) {
        iM[k,i]<-1
        iM[k,j]<-1
        k<-k+1
      }
    }
  }
  return(iM)
}
```

```
}
```

DEF. 4 (node degree). The degree of a node is the number of edges incident to that node. The sum of the degrees of the nodes of a graph is given by $2|E|$, since each edge is counted twice.

Figure 2. Directed graph, with 5 vertices, 7 edges, and one loop.

DEF. 5 (simple graph and multigraph). A graph with multiple connections between nodes is called multigraph. A graph with no multiple connections and no loops is called simple graph. Note that igraph does not seem to allow for multigraphs.

3 Directed graphs and weighted graphs

DEF. 6 (directed graph). When edges have a direction, we say that the graph is directed. In a directed graph, edges are represented by ordinate couples of numbers: the first number is the origin of the edge, and the second is the end. The adjacency matrix of a directed graph is not necessarily symmetric. The directed graph in Figure 2 is plotted by the following instructions in R:

```
# build the graph and plot it
edges<-c(1,2,1,5,2,3,3,5,5,3,4,5,4,3,4,4)
graph<-make_graph(edges=edges,directed=T)
plot(graph,vertex.size=20)
```

The adjacency matrix can be derived from the edges by the following function (that works also for undirected graphs):

```
# from edges to adjacency matrix
edges2aM<-function(edges) {
  Vertices<-unique(edges)
  V<-length(Vertices)
  aM<-matrix(0,nrow=V,ncol=V)
  rownames(aM)<-Vertices
  colnames(aM)<-Vertices
  for (i in seq(1,length(edges),2)) {
    vertex1<-edges[i]
    vertex2<-edges[i+1]
    aM[vertex1,vertex2]<-1
  }
}
```

```
return(aM)
}
```

By applying this function, we find that the adjacency matrix corresponding to the edges inputted and to the graph in Figure 2 is given by

$$M_a = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

DEF. 7 (weighted graph). In a weighted graph, each edge is associated with a weight, a scalar value that can be a measure of the strength of the link between the two nodes (the correlation in gene expression of two genes for instance) or the distance between two nodes, or the probability to pass from the state represented by one node to the state represented by the one it is connected to (like in Markov's chains). Weighted graphs can be directed or undirected. To define a weighted graph it is necessary to give more information than merely the edges. The following is the adjacency matrix of the graph in Figure 3:

$$M_a = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 4 & 16 & 14 & 0 \\ 0 & 6 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 12 & 0 & 0 & 40 \\ 0 & 0 & 10 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 40 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 3. Weighted and directed graph, with 5 vertices, 7 edges, and one loop.

To plot this graph from the adjacency matrix, I used the following commands. Note the arguments of the plot function:

```
# build the adjacency matrix
aM<-matrix(0,nrow=5,ncol=5)
aM[1,]<-c(0,4,16,14,0)
aM[2,]<-c(0,6,0,0,0)
aM[3,]<-c(0,12,0,0,40)
```

```

aM[4,]<-c(0,0,10,0,0)
aM[5,]<-c(0,0,40,0,0)

# build the graph from aM and plot it
graph<-graph_from_adjacency_matrix(aM,mode="directed",weighted=T)
plot(graph,
     edge.label=E(graph)$weight,
     adge.label.cex=0.2,
     vertex.size=20)

```

4 Paths and cycles

DEF. 8 (path). A path is any sequence of vertices that are connected by edges so that from any one of the vertices of a path it is possible to reach any other. Paths can be directed or undirected. A path is called *simple* when it does not include twice the same edge or the same node.

DEF. 9 (cycle). A path that starts and ends with the same node is called *cycle*. A cycle is simple, when it does not include twice the same node or the same edge if we exclude the starting and ending node.

DEF. 10 (length of a path). The number of edges of a path defines its length.

DEF. 11 (connection between nodes). Two nodes v_i, v_j are said connected if there is a path between them. They are strongly connected, if there is a path that starts in v_i and ends in v_j , and a path that starts in v_j and ends in v_i (this applies only to directed graphs. The connection between two nodes of an undirected graph is a binary relation that satisfies the properties of transitivity and symmetry. In the case of a directed graph, the relation is not symmetric, but it still is transitive. In a simple graph, where no loop is allowed, it can also be considered reflexive; therefore, it is a relation of equivalence and it defines classes of equivalence made up of nodes such that however we pick two of them, there is a path between them.

DEF. 12 (connected graph). An undirected graph is said *connected* if, for each pair of its nodes, there is a path between them. A directed graph is said *strongly connected* if each pair of nodes v_i, v_j there is a path from v_i to v_j and a path from v_j to v_i .

Figure 4. Number of edges for a connected graph, as a function of the number of nodes.

DEF. 13 (complete graph). A graph is said complete, if for each couple of nodes there an edge between them. The number of edges of a complete graph is given by the number of elements of the superior (or inferior) triangle of the adjacency matrix, or also by the number of combinations with no repetitions of class 2 extracted from V elements, that is

$$\text{Eq. 1} \quad E = \binom{V}{2} = \frac{V!}{(V-2)!2} = \frac{V(V-1)}{2}$$

This function is plotted in Figure 4.

DEF. 14 (acyclic graph). A directed graph with no simple cycles is called acyclic graph (Figure 5).

DEF. 15 (trees and forest). An undirected graph with no simple cycles is called forest. If it is connected, then it is called tree.

PROP. 1 (length of a path). In an undirected graph that is not weighted, with adjacency matrix A , the number of undirected paths of length r between v_i and v_j is given by the element ij of the r -th power of matrix A^n .

Proof. The number of paths between v_i and v_j with length one is given by a_{ij} . The number of paths of length 2 is given by

$$\sum_{k=1}^n a_{ik}a_{kj}$$

where n is the number of nodes of the graph. This sum is the element ij of matrix A^2 . To see this, consider that the paths of length 2 are only those that involve a third node v_k between v_i and v_j . Such a path does exist if and only if $a_{ik} = a_{kj} = 1$. Therefore their number is given by the sum we indicated above, which corresponds to element ij of matrix A^2 . And so forth ■

Figure 5. Acyclic graph.

4.1 Shortest path

PROP. 2 (Lemma). Given a simple graph with no orientation, let L_{ij} the shortest path between nodes v_i, v_j . Let v_k, v_h two other nodes included in L_{ij} (assuming that L_{ij} includes at least 4 nodes), then the path from v_k to v_h along L_{ij} (let us call it L_{kh}) is the shortest path between v_k and v_h .

Proof. Assume, for the sake of contradiction, that L_{kh} is not the shortest path between v_k and v_h . Then it follows that L_{ij} is not the shortest path between nodes v_i, v_j , which contradicts the hypothesis. Then it follows that L_{kh} must be the shortest path between v_k and v_h ■

PROP. 3 (Bellman's identity). Given a simple graph with no orientation, consider a subset S of its nodes and let us indicate L_{ij} the shortest path between nodes $v_i, v_j \in S$. For every node $v_k \notin S$ we define the function

$$\text{Eq. 2} \quad \Phi_{ik} = \min_{v_j \in S} (L_{ij} + a_{jk}), \quad v_k \notin S$$

where $a_{i,k}$ is the value of the adjacency matrix corresponding to the edge between v_i and v_k . Importantly, this minimum is calculated among those elements of the adjacency matrix that are different from zero. It can be shown that if

$$\text{Eq. 3} \quad \Phi_{ih} = \min_{v_k \notin S} \left(\min_{v_j \in S} (L_{ij} + a_{jk}) \right)$$

then the shortest path between v_h and v_i is Φ_{ih} (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Illustration for PROP. 3.

Proof. Let us indicate L_{ih} the shortest path between v_i and v_h . Since Φ_{ih} is a path between v_i and v_h , and L_{ih} is the shortest among the paths between v_i and v_h (by definition), it follows that $\Phi_{ih} \geq L_{ih}$. Now, we note that

$$\text{Eq. 4} \quad \Phi_{ih} = \min_{v_k \notin S} \left(\min_{v_j \in S} (L_{ij} + a_{jk}) \right) \leq L_{ij} + a_{jk}, \quad \begin{array}{l} \forall v_k \notin S \\ \forall v_j \in S \end{array}$$

We now consider the last node belonging to S along the path L_{ih} from i to h – let us call it v_p – and the first node outside S , let us call it v_q . Then we have

$$L_{ip} + a_{pq} \leq L_{ih}$$

where we have considered also that – according to PROP. 2 – L_{ip} is included in L_{ih} . Therefore, by substituting in Eq. 4 we have $\Phi_{ih} \leq L_{ip} + a_{pq} \leq L_{ih}$. And since $\Phi_{ih} \geq L_{ih}$, we must conclude that $\Phi_{ih} = L_{ih}$ ■

Example 1 (Dijkstra's algorithm). The previous proposition can be used to build a recursive algorithm for the determination – given a node $v_i \in V$ and a graph $\Gamma(V, E)$ – of the shortest paths L_{ij} for $v_j \in V$.

To introduce this algorithm, let us consider the weighted undirected and simple graph in Figure 7, whose adjacency matrix is

$$M_a = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 7 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 7 & 0 & 5 & 4 & 2 & 1 \\ 1 & 5 & 0 & 0 & 2 & 7 \\ 0 & 4 & 0 & 0 & 5 & 0 \\ 0 & 2 & 2 & 5 & 0 & 3 \\ 0 & 1 & 7 & 0 & 3 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

We want to determine the shortest path that connects each one of its nodes to v_1 .

Iteration 1. We consider the subset of nodes $S = \{v_1\}$ and we search for $\min_{v_k \notin S} \left(\min_{v_j \in S} (L_{1j} + a_{1k}) \right)$, where $L_{11} = 0$. If we inspect M_a , we conclude that the minimum is reached for v_3 and we have $L_{13} = 1$. We start building a table with the shortest paths (Table 1).

Iteration 2. We now consider the subset $S = \{v_1, v_3\}$ and we search for $\min_{v_k \notin S} \left(\min_{v_j \in S} (L_{1j} + a_{jk}) \right)$. We have

$$\Phi_{1,2} = \min_{v_j \in S} (L_{1j} + a_{j2}) = \min_{v_j \in S} (L_{1,3} + a_{3,2}, L_{1,1} + a_{1,2}) = \min_{v_j \in S} (1 + 5, 0 + 7) = 6$$

$$\Phi_{1,4} = \min_{v_j \in S} (L_{1,3} + a_{3,4}, L_{1,1} + a_{1,4}) = \min_{v_j \in S} (1 + \infty, 0 + \infty) = \infty$$

$$\Phi_{1,5} = \min_{v_j \in S} (L_{1j} + a_{j5}) = \min_{v_j \in S} (L_{1,3} + a_{3,5}, L_{1,1} + a_{1,5}) = \min_{v_j \in S} (1 + 2, 0 + \infty) = 3$$

$$\Phi_{1,6} = \min_{v_j \in S} (L_{1j} + a_{j6}) = \min_{v_j \in S} (L_{1,3} + a_{3,6}, L_{1,1} + a_{1,6}) = \min_{v_j \in S} (1 + 7, 0 + \infty) = 8$$

The conclusion is that we have found the shortest path for v_5 and it is $L_{1,5} = 3$.

Iteration	$\Phi_{1,2}$	$\Phi_{1,3}$	$\Phi_{1,4}$	$\Phi_{1,5}$	$\Phi_{1,6}$
1	7	$L_{1,3} = 1$	∞	∞	∞
2	6	-	∞	$L_{1,5} = 3$	8
3	$L_{1,2} = 5$	-	8	-	6
4	-	-	8	-	$L_{1,6} = 6$
5	-	-	$L_{1,4} = 8$	-	-

Table 1. Shortest paths for Example 1.

Iteration 3. Consider the subset $S = \{v_1, v_3, v_5\}$. We calculate:

$$\Phi_{1,2} = \min_{v_j \in S} (L_{1,5} + a_{5,2}, L_{1,3} + a_{3,2}, L_{1,1} + a_{1,2}) = \min_{v_j \in S} (3 + 2, 1 + 5, 0 + 7) = 5$$

$$\Phi_{1,4} = \min_{v_j \in S} (L_{1,5} + a_{5,4}, L_{1,3} + a_{3,4}, L_{1,1} + a_{1,4}) = \min_{v_j \in S} (3 + 5, 1 + \infty, 0 + \infty) = 8$$

$$\Phi_{1,6} = \min_{v_j \in S} (L_{1,5} + a_{5,6}, L_{1,3} + a_{3,6}, L_{1,1} + a_{1,6}) = \min_{v_j \in S} (3 + 3, 1 + 7, 0 + \infty) = 6$$

Iteration 4. Consider the subset $S = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_5\}$. We calculate:

$$\Phi_{1,4} = \min_{v_j \in S} (L_{1,5} + a_{5,4}, L_{1,3} + a_{3,4}, L_{1,2} + a_{2,4}, L_{1,1} + a_{1,4}) = \min_{v_j \in S} (3 + 5, 1 + \infty, 5 + 4, 0 + \infty) = 8$$

$$\Phi_{1,6} = \min_{v_j \in S} (L_{1,5} + a_{5,6}, L_{1,3} + a_{3,6}, L_{1,2} + a_{2,6}, L_{1,1} + a_{1,6}) = \min_{v_j \in S} (3 + 3, 1 + 7, 5 + 1, 0 + \infty) = 6$$

Iteration 5. Consider the subset $S = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_5, v_6\}$. We calculate:

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_{1,4} &= \min_{v_j \in S} (L_{1,6} + a_{6,4}, L_{1,5} + a_{5,4}, L_{1,3} + a_{3,4}, L_{1,2} + a_{2,4}, L_{1,1} + a_{1,4}) = \\ &= \min_{v_j \in S} (6 + \infty, 3 + 5, 1 + \infty, 5 + 4, 0 + \infty) = 8 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 7. Illustration for Example 1.

In R, the shortest distances from v_1 for our graph can be easily obtained with the following lines of code:

```
# file name: shortest_path.R

library(igraph)

# build the adjacency matrix
aM<-matrix(0,nrow=6,ncol=6)
aM[1,]<-c(0,7,1,0,0,0)
aM[2,]<-c(7,0,5,4,2,1)
aM[3,]<-c(1,5,0,0,2,7)
```

```

aM[4,]<-c(0,4,0,0,5,0)
aM[5,]<-c(0,2,2,5,0,3)
aM[6,]<-c(0,1,7,0,3,0)

# build the graph from aM and plot it
graph<-graph_from_adjacency_matrix(aM,mode="undirected",weighted=T)
plot(graph,
     edge.label=E(graph)$weight,
     adge.label.cex=0.2,
     vertex.size=20)

# Compute shortest paths from A using Dijkstra's algorithm
dijkstra_distances<-distances(graph,v=1,weights=E(graph)$weight)

```

The output is the following table:

	[,1]	[,2]	[,3]	[,4]	[,5]	[,6]
[1,]	0	5	1	8	3	6

This algorithm can be applied to directed graphs as well, in this case, paths are allowed only in certain directions, therefore it is a bit more complex to apply the rules. To perform the calculation automatically in R for a directed graph, add the argument `mode="out"` to `distances()` and also define the graph as directed, when you build it from the adjacency matrix.

5 Planar graphs

DEF. 16 (planar graph). We say that a simple graph is planar if we can draw it on a plane in a way such that its edges only intercept at their extremities. Note that the graph in Figure 7 is planar, despite the appearance, because we can draw the edge between nodes 2 and 6 with a curve that does not intercept any other edges. It can be recognized that a planar graph is such that its edges divide the plane in regions (called *faces*) that are delimited by at least three edges. We indicated the number of these regions with F . Note that we consider among the faces also the outer one, that includes within itself the whole graph. Note also that there are always two faces for each edge. Therefore, the total number of edges must satisfy the inequality

$$\text{Eq. 5} \quad E \geq \frac{3}{2}F$$

PROP. 4 (Euler's formula). It can be shown that in a planar graph with F faces (including the outer one), V nodes, and E edges, it must be

$$\text{Eq. 6} \quad F = E - V + 2$$

Proof. Omitted ■

PROP. 5 (necessary condition). A necessary condition for planarity of a simple graph is

$$\text{Eq. 7} \quad E \leq 3V - 6$$

Proof. From Euler's formula and Eq. 5 we have

$$F = E - V + 2 \leq \frac{2}{3}E \Leftrightarrow 3E - 3V + 6 \leq 2E \Leftrightarrow E \leq 3V - 6$$

If this condition is not satisfied, the graph cannot be planar. In other words, if a graph is planar, then $E \leq 3V - 6$. In general, it is not true the contrary. Therefore we can say that if this condition is not true, then the graph is not planar ■

Example 2 (complete graph). In complete graphs we have that the number of edges is given by Eq. 1. Then we can wonder when a connected graph cannot be planar by considering PROP. 5. The necessary condition for planarity of a connected graph becomes

$$\frac{V^2 - V}{2} \leq 3V - 6 \Leftrightarrow V^2 - 7V + 12 \leq 0$$

It is easy to verify that the necessary condition is satisfied only when $3 \leq V \leq 4$. Therefore connected graphs with more than 4 nodes cannot be planar. The case of $V < 3$ is not of particular interest. Put simply, planar graphs must have a number of edges of the same order of the number of nodes, while connected graphs have a number of edges of the same order of V^2 .

6 Graphs and Markov chains

DEF. 17 (Markov chain). Given a discrete random variable X that varies with time (a stochastic process), we say that i follows a Markov's chain if

$$P(X_n = j | X_k = i_k, k = 1, 2, \dots, n - 1) = P(X_n = j | X_{n-1} = i)$$

where X_n is the value assumed by the random variable at the instant t_n . Note that we are here saying that a discrete stochastic process is a Markov chain if the value assumed at time t_n depends only on the value assumed at time t_{n-1} . We introduce the notation

$$\text{Eq. 8} \quad p_{ij}(n) = P(X_n = j | X_{n-1} = i)$$

If the number of possible values that can be assumed by X is finite, we have a finite Markov chain.

DEF. 18 (homogeneous Markov chain). Note that, in general, $p_{ij}(n)$ is a function of the instant t_n considered. It is, in other words, a numerical sequence, a function of time. If $p_{ij}(n)$ happens to be constant with respect to time, however, we select the states i, j , then we say that the Markov chain is homogeneous. In this document, we consider only homogeneous Markov chains and we use the following notation

$$\text{Eq. 9} \quad p_{ij} = P(X_n = j | X_{n-1} = i)$$

$$\text{Eq. 10} \quad p_{ij}^{(m)} = P(X_{n+m} = j | X_n = i)$$

where $p_{ij}^{(m)}$ is the probability that the random variables assume value j at time t_{n+m} if it assumed value i at time t_n . This value does not depend on n !

DEF. 19 (transition matrix and associated graph). In a finite Markov chain with a total of V possible states, the possible values p_{ij} for $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, V$, the matrix whose element ij is given by p_{ij} is called transition matrix. The transition matrix can be seen as an adjacency matrix of a weighted directed graph. Therefore, any homogenous and finite Markov chain is associated with a weighted and directed graph.

PROP. 6 (properties). In a finite homogenous Markov chain with a total of V possible states the following properties can be proved:

$$\text{Eq. 11} \quad \sum_{j=1}^V p_{ij} = 1$$

$$\text{Eq. 12} \quad p_{ij}^{(m+n)} = \sum_{h=1}^V p_{ih}^{(m)} p_{hj}^{(n)}$$

$$\text{Eq. 13} \quad p_{ii}^{(n)} \geq p_{ii}^n$$

$$\text{Eq. 14} \quad M^{(n)} = M^n$$

where M is the transition matrix. The probabilities of reaching each one of the states, at time t_n if the probabilities at time zero are given by the row vector $\mathbf{p}^{(0)}$ are described by the row vector

$$\text{Eq. 15} \quad \mathbf{p}^{(n)} = \mathbf{p}^{(0)} M^{(n)} = \mathbf{p}^{(0)} M^n$$

where the i -th element of $\mathbf{p}^{(n)}$ is the probability of reaching state i at time t_n if the probabilities of starting from each one of the states at time t_0 are given by vector $\mathbf{p}^{(0)}$.

Proof. Omitted, see for instance chapter 5 of (1) or chapter 4 of (8) ■

Example 3 (two players). Let us consider a game with two players, A and B. The game is a series of matches, such that at the end of each match there is a transition of money from one player to the other. Let X_0 euro be the starting budget of A and Y_0 the starting budget of B. Let p be the probability that at any given match, player A loses one euro; then $q = 1 - p$ is the probability that player B wins one euro, at any given match. If we indicate with X_n the amount of money of player A at the end of match n , we have that X_n is a homogeneous Markov chain. It is also finite, if we assume that the game stops when one player cannot pay is debt. In particular, let us say that at each match the maximum amount of euros that can be won or lost is m , and let us model the probability for A to win a $k \leq m$ euros in a match as a Binomial distribution. We can write:

$$\begin{aligned} P(X_n = X_{n-1} + U_n) &= P(X_n = X_{n-1} + k - (m - k)) = \\ &= P(X_n = X_{n-1} + 2k - m) = \binom{m}{k} p^k (1 - p)^{m-k} \end{aligned}$$

We can now build the transition matrix:

$$\text{Eq. 16} \quad p_{ij} = P(X_n = j | X_{n-1} = i) = \binom{m}{\frac{j-1+m}{2}} p^{\frac{j-1+m}{2}} (1 - p)^{m - \frac{j-1+m}{2}}$$

where I have considered that $2k - m = j - i \Rightarrow k = \frac{j-1+m}{2}$. The number of euros won by A at each match can be anywhere from 0 to m (we only consider integer values), therefore we have

$$\frac{j-1+m}{2} = 0, 1, 2, \dots, m \Leftrightarrow j = i - m, i + 2 - m, i + 4 - m, i + 6 - m, \dots, i + m$$

Moreover, the generic state must satisfy the condition $0 \leq X_n \leq X_0 + Y_0$ (the chain is finite, as anticipated): when $X_n = 0$ player B has won, when $X_n = X_0 + Y_0$ player A has won. To satisfy Eq.

11, we must consider the cases where A loses more than he has and add the probabilities for these cases to the state $X_n = 0$; same for the state $X_n = X_0 + Y_0$, we assume that this state is reached even for those matches where B loses more than he has. All that said, setting parameters as

$$m = 4, X_0 = Y_0 = 6, p = 0.7$$

we can build the transition matrix in Table 2 and the associated weighted directed graph in Figure 8.

	0	2	4	6	8	10	12
0	0.3483	0.4116	0.2401	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
2	0.0837	0.2646	0.4116	0.2401	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
4	0.0081	0.0756	0.2646	0.4116	0.2401	0.0000	0.0000
6	0.0000	0.0081	0.0756	0.2646	0.4116	0.2401	0.0000
8	0.0000	0.0000	0.0081	0.0756	0.2646	0.4116	0.2401
10	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0081	0.0756	0.2646	0.6517
12	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0081	0.0756	0.9163

Table 2. Transition matrix for the Markov chain of Example 3.

Figure 8. Graph associated with the transition matrix in Table 2.

DEF. 20 (irreducibility). If the graph associated with a finite Markov chain is connected, we say that the chain is said *irreducible*. The Markov chain of Example 3 is irreducible.

DEF. 21 (invariant measure). Given transition matrix M , we define *invariant measure* any row vector $\boldsymbol{\pi}$ such that $\boldsymbol{\pi}M = \boldsymbol{\pi}$ and $\sum_{i=1}^V \pi_i = 1$, with π_i the i -th element of $\boldsymbol{\pi}$. The invariant measure is also called *stationary distribution* or *invariant distribution*).

PROP. 7 (unique invariant). If a Markov chain is irreducible (that is: its graph is connected) and there is at least one state h such that $p_{hh} > 0$ (that is: there is at least one loop in the associated graph) then this chain has an invariant, it is unique and

$$\text{Eq. 17} \quad \pi_j = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} p_{ij}^{(n)} \quad \forall i, j = 1, 2, \dots, V$$

Example 4 (two players). Consider again the Markov chain of Example 2. The graph is connected and there are loops, therefore this Markov chain admits a unique invariant (PROP. 7). To calculate the invariant with R, we can use `igraph`. In particular, let us say that M is the transition matrix, then the invariant is given by the following lines of code:

```
eig<-eigen(t(M))
invariant<-abs(eig$eigenvectors[,1])
invariant<-invariant/sum(invariant)
```


Figure 9. Convergence of the elements of the transition matrix towards the invariant measure.

Figure 10. Evolution of the distribution of probability of the states, from an initial distribution $\mathbf{p}^{(0)} = \left[\frac{1}{7} \ \frac{1}{7} \ \frac{1}{7} \ \frac{1}{7} \ \frac{1}{7} \ \frac{1}{7} \ \frac{1}{7} \right]$.

As you can see, we search for the eigenvector of the transpose of the transition matrix, then we normalize the solution (we already know that there is a unique solution). It is also interesting to verify Eq. 17 in this case. To do so, we calculate the exponential of the transition matrix and we plot its elements as a function of the exponent, as in Figure 9. It is also possible to study the evolution in time of $\mathbf{p}^{(n)}$ for a given $\mathbf{p}^{(0)}$ (see Eq. 15). For

$$\mathbf{p}^{(0)} = \left[\frac{1}{7} \quad \frac{1}{7} \quad \frac{1}{7} \quad \frac{1}{7} \quad \frac{1}{7} \quad \frac{1}{7} \quad \frac{1}{7} \right]$$

we obtain Figure 10. The script that solves this example and that generates all the figures is reported below.

```
# file name: gambler
#
# year: 2024 - month: 3 - day: 27
#
library(igraph) # for graph_from_adjacency_matrix()
library(expm) # for power of a matrix
#
# parameters of the game
#
m<-4 # upper limit that can be win or lost in a match
X0<-6 # initial budget of player A
Y0<-6 # initial budget of player B
p<-0.7 # probability for player A to win one euro during a match
q<-1-p # probability for player B to win one euro during a match
#
# transition matrix
#
states<-seq(0,X0+Y0,by=2)
N<-length(states) # number of states
M<-matrix(data=NA,nrow=N,ncol=N)
colnames(M)<-states
rownames(M)<-states
for (h in 1:N) {
  i<-states[h]
  for (k in 1:N) {
    j<-states[k]
    M[h,k]<-dbinom((j-i+m)/2,m,p)
  }
}
#
M2<-M
for (h in 1:N) {
  M2[h,1]<-sum(M[h:N,1])
  M2[h,N]<-sum(M[1:h,N])
}
M<-M2
#
# graph
#
graph<-graph_from_adjacency_matrix(M,mode="directed",weighted=TRUE)
plot(graph,edge.label=E(graph)$weight)
#
# steps
#
```

```

p0<-rep(1/13,N)
p<-p0%*%(M%^5)
#
# invariant
#
eig<-eigen(t(M))
invariant<-abs(eig$vector[,1])
invariant<-invariant/sum(invariant)
#
# limit of the transition matrix
#
n<-20 # number of steps
M.list<-list()
for (s in 1:n) {
  M.list[[s]]<-M%^s
}
#
col.v<-c() # for colors in plot
h<-1
for (i in 1:N) {
  for (j in 1:N) {
    vector<-c()
    for (s in 1:n) {
      mat<-M.list[[s]]
      vector[s]<-mat[i,j]
    }
    col.v[h]<-j
    h<-h+1
    if (i+j==2) plot(seq(1:n),vector,xlim=c(1,n),ylim=c(0,1),type="l",lty=1,col=j,
      lwd=2,xlab="steps",ylab=expression(p[ij]))
    if (i+j>2) plot(seq(1:n),vector,xlim=c(1,n),ylim=c(0,1),type="l",lty=1,col=j,
      lwd=2,xlab="",ylab="")
    if (i+j<2*N) par(new=T)
  }
}
#
# limit of the density
#
n<-20
p<-list()
p[[1]]<-rep(1/N,N)
for (s in 2:n) {
  p[[s]]<-p[[s-1]]%*%M.list[[s]]
}
for (i in 1:N) {
  vector<-c()
  for (s in 1:n) {
    v.p<-p[[s]]
    vector[s]<-v.p[i]
  }
  if (i==1) plot(seq(1:n),vector,xlim=c(1,n),ylim=c(0,1),type="l",lty=1,col=i,
    lwd=2,xlab="steps",ylab="Probability")
  if (i>1) plot(seq(1:n),vector,xlim=c(1,n),ylim=c(0,1),type="l",lty=1,col=i,
    lwd=2,xlab="",ylab="")
  if (i<N) par(new=T)
}

```

6.1 Random walk with restart

DEF. 22 (RWR). We show now how to derive from a weighted and connected graph a Markov chain with a unique invariant that can be used to measure the connection of the nodes of the original graph to a specific subset of its nodes. Let M be the transition matrix of an irreducible Markov chain, then consider the distribution of probabilities defined by the following law

$$\text{Eq. 18} \quad \mathbf{p}^{(n)} = (1 - \gamma)\mathbf{p}^{(n-1)}M + \gamma\mathbf{p}^{(0)}, \quad \gamma \in]0,1[$$

where γ is called back-probability. This is a stochastic process called *Random Walk with Restart* (RWR). We'll see that it represents a powerful tool for the study of gene networks (9).

PROP. 8 (Lemma). Given a square matrix M and a numeric series $\{a_k\}$, if there is a matrix norm such that $\sum_{k=0}^n \|M\|^k |a_k|$ is bounded, then

$$\text{Eq. 19} \quad \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} M^k a_k = L \in]-\infty, \infty[$$

In particular – for $a_k = 1 \forall k$ – we have

$$\text{Eq. 20} \quad \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} M^k = (I - M)^{-1}$$

Moreover, if there is a matrix norm such that $\|M\| < 1$ we have

$$\text{Eq. 21} \quad \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} M^k = 0$$

Proof. This is theorem 5.6.15 (page 300) and 5.6.11, respectively, of (10) ■

PROP. 9 (not a Markov chain). The random walk with restart in Eq. 18 is not a Markov chain (the value assumed at time t_n depends from both the value assumed at time t_0 and t_{n-1}), and it is not homogenous. Its transition matrix is given by Eq. 22 and the distribution of probabilities of its states converges to $\mathbf{p}^{(0)}\gamma(I - (1 - \gamma)M)^{-1}$.

Proof. In what follows we derive the transition matrix of the process in Eq. 18. I start calculating the transition matrix for a few first iterations, to get an idea of what the form of the transition matrix $T^{(n)}$ may be. For $n = 1$ we have

$$\mathbf{p}^{(1)} = (1 - \gamma)\mathbf{p}^{(0)}M + \gamma\mathbf{p}^{(0)} = \mathbf{p}^{(0)}((1 - \gamma)M + \gamma I)$$

Therefore, $T^{(1)} = (1 - \gamma)M + \gamma I$. For $n = 2$ we must use the expression found for $\mathbf{p}^{(1)}$ and we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{p}^{(2)} &= (1 - \gamma)\mathbf{p}^{(1)}M + \gamma\mathbf{p}^{(0)} = \\ &= (1 - \gamma)\mathbf{p}^{(0)}((1 - \gamma)M + \gamma I)M + \gamma\mathbf{p}^{(0)} = \mathbf{p}^{(0)}((1 - \gamma)^2 M^2 + (1 - \gamma)\gamma M + \gamma I) \end{aligned}$$

Then, $T^{(2)} = (1 - \gamma)^2 M^2 + (1 - \gamma)\gamma M + \gamma I$. For $n = 3$ we find

$$\mathbf{p}^{(3)} = (1 - \gamma)\mathbf{p}^{(2)}M + \gamma\mathbf{p}^{(0)} = \mathbf{p}^{(0)}((1 - \gamma)^3 M^3 + \gamma(1 - \gamma)^2 M^2 + \gamma(1 - \gamma)M + \gamma I)$$

Hence, $T^{(3)} = (1 - \gamma)^3 M^3 + \gamma(1 - \gamma)^2 M^2 + \gamma(1 - \gamma)M + \gamma I$. The suspect is that the transition matrix can be expressed as

$$\text{Eq. 22} \quad T^{(n)} = (1 - \gamma)^n M^n + \gamma \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (1 - \gamma)^k M^k$$

To prove this, we can proceed by induction. We assume true this formula for $n - 1$ and we show that it holds for n . For $n - 1$ we can write

$$T^{(n-1)} = (1 - \gamma)^{n-1} M^{n-1} + \gamma \sum_{k=0}^{n-2} (1 - \gamma)^k M^k$$

Therefore, the probabilities of the states for $n - 1$ are

$$\mathbf{p}^{(n-1)} = \mathbf{p}^{(0)} T^{(n-1)} = \mathbf{p}^{(0)} \left((1 - \gamma)^{n-1} M^{n-1} + \gamma \sum_{k=0}^{n-2} (1 - \gamma)^k M^k \right)$$

By substituting this expression in Eq. 18 we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{p}^{(n)} &= (1 - \gamma) \mathbf{p}^{(n-1)} M + \gamma \mathbf{p}^{(0)} = \\ &= (1 - \gamma) \mathbf{p}^{(0)} \left((1 - \gamma)^{n-1} M^{n-1} + \gamma \sum_{k=0}^{n-2} (1 - \gamma)^k M^k \right) M + \gamma \mathbf{p}^{(0)} = \\ &= (1 - \gamma) \mathbf{p}^{(0)} \left((1 - \gamma)^{n-1} M^n + \gamma \sum_{k=0}^{n-2} (1 - \gamma)^k M^{k+1} \right) + \gamma \mathbf{p}^{(0)} I = \\ &= \mathbf{p}^{(0)} \left((1 - \gamma)^n M^n + \gamma \sum_{k=0}^{n-2} (1 - \gamma)^{k+1} M^{k+1} + \gamma I \right) \end{aligned}$$

We operate the substitution $h = k + 1$ in the sum and we get

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{p}^{(n)} &= \mathbf{p}^{(0)} \left((1 - \gamma)^n M^n + \gamma \sum_{h=1}^{n-1} (1 - \gamma)^h M^h + \gamma I \right) = \\ &= \mathbf{p}^{(0)} \left((1 - \gamma)^n M^n + \gamma \sum_{h=0}^{n-1} (1 - \gamma)^h M^h \right) \end{aligned}$$

Then, Eq. 22 is proved. What about the limit $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} T^{(n)}$? Now, we can say that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (1 - \gamma)^n M^n = 0$$

according to PROP. 8 (Eq. 21), because the sum of the elements of any row of matrix $(1 - \gamma)M$ is less than 1, in other words $\|(1 - \gamma)M\|_\infty < 1$. Therefore, we have

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} T^{(n)} = \gamma \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{h=0}^{n-1} (1 - \gamma)^h M^h$$

If we consider again PROP. 8 we have that the sums $\sum_{h=0}^{n-1} (1 - \gamma)^h \|M\|_\infty^h$ are bounded, in fact

$$\sum_{h=0}^{n-1} (1-\gamma)^h \|M\|_{\infty}^h = \sum_{h=0}^{n-1} (1-\gamma)^h = \frac{1 - (1-\gamma)^n}{\gamma} \rightarrow \frac{1}{\gamma}$$

Therefore, according to Eq. 20, we conclude that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{h=0}^{n-1} (1-\gamma)^h M^h = (I - (1-\gamma)M)^{-1}$$

This means that $T^{(n)}$ converges to $\gamma(I - (1-\gamma)M)^{-1}$ ■

6.2 RWR and gene networks

Example 5 (ME/CFS). In this example, I show, with real experimental data, how to use graph theory and RWR to study a network of genes associated with a phenotype. Let us consider the genes collected in Table 3 from two GWAS studies and associated with Myalgic Encephalomyelitis/Chronic Fatigue Syndrome, according to various criteria. Each gene has been used as a seed for a search of known interacting genes employing STRING, a database of gene pairs with a computed probability of interaction or score, available as a web-based service or via a dedicated API (4). From the original 12 genes, we obtain a list of 79 genes.

The final list of genes is used to build a weighted undirected graph, with a node for each gene and an edge for each couple of genes with a STRING score greater than zero.

We consider the adjacency matrix of this graph and normalize it so that it satisfies Eq. 11 (row normalization). Let M be the adjacency matrix (also a transition matrix). We define $\mathbf{p}^{(0)}$ so that its elements are either zero (if they correspond to predicted genes) or $1/12$ (if they correspond to experimental genes). We then calculate the asymptotic distribution of probability of the random walk with restart built from matrix M , according to DEF. 22. By PROP. 9 we have that it is given by $\mathbf{p}^{(0)}\gamma(I - (1-\gamma)M)^{-1}$. Once we have built matrix M , to perform the RWR we can use the following lines of codes:

```
V<-nrow(M) # number of states/genes/nodes
gamma<-0.3 # back probability
p0<-rep(0,nrow(M)) # starting distribution
for (i in 1:V) {
  gene.type<-all.genes.unique$source[i]
  gene.type<-str_split(gene.type,"/")[1]
  if ("E"%in%gene.type) p0[i]<-1/nrow(Exper_list)
}
I<-diag(V) # identity matrix
p<-p0%*%ginv(I - (1-gamma)*M)*gamma # stationary probability
```

We obtain, at the end of this process, the stationary probabilities indicated as scores in Table 4. What is the meaning of this scoring system? The idea is that in a random walk with restart, the stationary probability is an index of the connectivity between each node of the graph and the starting nodes (the experimental or seed genes, in our case). Why do we need to rank the genes of the expanded list? This allows for using this list in gene set analysis, where a rank is required.

Figure 11. Weighted directed graph generated by protein-protein interaction scores retrieved from STRING API. The original seed genes are 12 (Table 3). The list includes 79 genes.

List name	Genes	Cases	Sex	Phenotype	Description	Ref.
UKBB.CFS	<i>CYCSP34, SLC25A15, SUGTIP3, MRPS31</i>	1208	F	self-reported CFS (PHESANT)	Expression affected (eQTL) by two common variants (rs1536807, rs2017696) associated with phenotype in standard GWAS-type analysis ($p < 5.0E-08$)	(11)
UKBB.CFS	<i>TPTE2</i>	1208	F	self-reported CFS (PHESANT)	A common variant (rs11147812) on a corresponding unprocessed pseudogene (TPTE2P5) is associated with phenotype in standard GWAS-type analysis ($p < 5.0E-08$)	(11)
UKBB.CFS	<i>EBF3</i>	1659	F/M	self-reported CFS (PHESANT)	Harboring a rare variant (rs148723539) of possible regulatory function (score 5 on RegulomeDB) associated with phenotype in standard GWAS-type analysis ($p < 1.0E-08$)	(11)
UKBB.R53	<i>ATP8B1</i>	362	M	ICD10: R53	Expression affected (eQTL) by a common variant (rs62092652) associated with phenotype in standard GWAS-type analysis ($p < 5.0E-08$)	(11)
UKBB. R53	<i>NUPR2, CHCHD2</i>	456	F	ICD10: R53	Expression affected (eQTL) by an uncommon variant (rs182581502) associated with phenotype in standard GWAS-type analysis ($p < 1.0E-08$)	(11)
NOR.CFS	<i>TPPP</i>	427	F/M	ME/CFS (CCC)	Weak associative signal between intronic regions of this gene and ME/CFS in standard GWAS-type analysis ($p < 8.5E-07$)	(12)
NOR.CFS	<i>ZDHHC11, ZDHHC11B</i>	427	F/M	ME/CFS (CCC)	Expression affected (eQTL) by a common variant (rs139264145) associated with phenotype ($p < 8.5E-07$)	(12)

Table 3. Genes experimentally associated with ME/CFS, by various criteria.

name	score	Predicted	Predictor	list.name	source
CYCSP34	0.025			UKBB.CFS	E
SLC25A15	0.031652	ASL/NAGS/OAT/ASS1/FAAP24/MTCH1/HNRNPA2B1		UKBB.CFS	E
MRPS31	0.030532	MRPS23/PTCD3/MRPS33/MRPS24/MRPS22/MRPS9/MRPS35/MRPS7/MRPS14		UKBB.CFS	E
SUGT1P3	0.025			UKBB.CFS	E
TPTE2	0.029497	MTMR6/GUCY1A2/PTEN/AKT1		UKBB.CFS	E
EBF3	0.035149	DCUN1D1/EBF2/CPNE4/TMTC1/ZNF423		UKBB.CFS	E
ATP8B1	0.031475	TMEM30B/ATP10D/ATP10B/ATP10A/ATP11A/ATP8A1/NR1H4/ABCB11		UKBB.R53	E
NUPR2	0.032179	TPP1/TERF1/POT1/ACD/TINF2/TP53INP2		UKBB.R53	E
CHCHD2	0.032493	CHCHD10/ATP5PD/COX4I1/VPS35/PARK7/PLA2G6/CHCHD4		UKBB.R53	E
TPPP	0.034641	ACTR3B/DCTN1/CAPZA1/CAPZA2/DCTN4/DCTN2/HDAC6/SNCA		NOR.CFS	E
ZDHHC11	0.033361	ZDHHC20/ZDHHC13/ZDHHC8/ZDHHC9/ZDHHC5/ZDHHC3/GOLGA7/ZDHHC23/ZDHHC22		NOR.CFS	E
ZDHHC11B	0.032582	ZDHHC13/TMEM170A/SPDYE11/SPDYE8P/SPDYE9P		NOR.CFS	E
ASL	0.005509		SLC25A15	UKBB.CFS	P
NAGS	0.006645		SLC25A15	UKBB.CFS	P
OAT	0.006596		SLC25A15	UKBB.CFS	P
ASS1	0.007491		SLC25A15	UKBB.CFS	P
FAAP24	0.002819		SLC25A15	UKBB.CFS	P
MTCH1	0.004725		SLC25A15	UKBB.CFS	P
HNRNPA2B1	0.007893		SLC25A15	UKBB.CFS	P
MRPS23	0.007193		MRPS31	UKBB.CFS	P
PTCD3	0.007228		MRPS31	UKBB.CFS	P
MRPS33	0.008643		MRPS31	UKBB.CFS	P
MRPS24	0.007951		MRPS31	UKBB.CFS	P
MRPS22	0.008094		MRPS31	UKBB.CFS	P
MRPS9	0.010749		MRPS31	UKBB.CFS	P
MRPS35	0.009256		MRPS31	UKBB.CFS	P
MRPS7	0.011691		MRPS31	UKBB.CFS	P
MRPS14	0.009915		MRPS31	UKBB.CFS	P
MTMR6	0.004258		TPTE2	UKBB.CFS	P
GUCY1A2	0.004497		TPTE2	UKBB.CFS	P
PTEN	0.010087		TPTE2	UKBB.CFS	P

AKT1	0.013028
DCUN1D1	0.005116
EBF2	0.009888
CPNE4	0.004228
TMTC1	0.009262
ZNF423	0.009157
TMEM30B	0.00639
ATP10D	0.006508
ATP10B	0.00754
ATP10A	0.006501
ATP11A	0.007332
ATP8A1	0.006833
NR1H4	0.00598
ABCB11	0.00576
TPP1	0.009532
TERF1	0.012294
POT1	0.009165
ACD	0.007517
TINF2	0.008693
TP53INP2	0.003405
CHCHD10	0.006633
ATP5PD	0.007057
COX4I1	0.00692
VPS35	0.012581
PARK7	0.013066
PLA2G6	0.006353
CHCHD4	0.004067
ACTR3B	0.005801
DCTN1	0.010251
CAPZA1	0.006683
CAPZA2	0.007267
DCTN4	0.006896
DCTN2	0.007946

TPTE2	UKBB.CFS	P
EBF3	UKBB.CFS	P
ATP8B1	UKBB.R53	P
NUPR2	UKBB.R53	P
CHCHD2	UKBB.R53	P
TPPP	NOR.CFS	P

HDAC6	0.00657	TPPP	NOR.CFS	P
SNCA	0.010408	TPPP	NOR.CFS	P
ZDHHC20	0.009384	ZDHHC11	NOR.CFS	P
ZDHHC13	0.009124	ZDHHC11/ZDHHC11B	NOR.CFS	P/P
ZDHHC8	0.008421	ZDHHC11	NOR.CFS	P
ZDHHC9	0.00749	ZDHHC11	NOR.CFS	P
ZDHHC5	0.009495	ZDHHC11	NOR.CFS	P
ZDHHC3	0.009938	ZDHHC11	NOR.CFS	P
GOLGA7	0.008561	ZDHHC11	NOR.CFS	P
ZDHHC23	0.00707	ZDHHC11	NOR.CFS	P
ZDHHC22	0.010174	ZDHHC11	NOR.CFS	P
TMEM170A	0.002232	ZDHHC11B	NOR.CFS	P
SPDYE11	0.004513	ZDHHC11B	NOR.CFS	P
SPDYE8P	0.004706	ZDHHC11B	NOR.CFS	P
SPDYE9P	0.004796	ZDHHC11B	NOR.CFS	P

Table 4. Genes experimentally associated with ME/CFS, and genes derived from them by STRING API. The score is the stationary probability of the associated random walk with restart.

7 References

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